

TERRORISM AS A CHANGING PATTERN OF ARMED CONFLICT IN AFRICA: ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW.

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on terrorism as a changing pattern of conflict in Africa and the role that International Humanitarian Law (IHL) plays. It does this by analysing the rise of terrorist insurgency through guerilla warfare and terrorist attacks, international (territorial) armed conflicts and non-international (internal) armed conflicts in Africa, in order to distinguish between the legal frameworks governing IHL and Terrorism. The article proffers that to a large extent, IHL in the provisions of its instruments does not play a strong role in dealing with terrorism not only in Africa but elsewhere in the globe.

1.0 Introduction

Africa, throughout the second half of the twentieth century has been wrecked by internal conflicts and civil wars. In this first half of the twenty first century, Africa in contrast to the end of the last century, is witnessing a new pattern of armed conflicts. The conflicts in South Sudan, the armed strife in the Niger Delta region of southern Nigeria, the Al-shabab armed struggle in Somalia, the gunmen invasion of northern Mali and the Boko Haram insurgency in northern Nigeria are some of the new pattern of armed conflicts in the continent. Many political analysts have described such conflicts as the products of partisan politics while some linked the cause of these conflicts to tribalism, sectarianism and ethnic cleansing. The nature of war and armed conflicts in Africa is changing from time to time according to the different political and social situations of the continent. For example, anti-colonial wars of the 1950s and 1960s, gave way to border conflicts of 1960s and 1970s, but from the 1980s to date we have been witnessing more intra-state (internal strife) than inter-state armed conflicts. This changing nature of conflict is itself an interesting subject of further study and analysis.

Since the end of the Cold War, civil war has become the predominant form of violence globally¹. For example, of the 25 major armed conflicts listed by the Stockholm International

* Abdulkadir Mubarak Ph.D, LL.M, LL.B, Senior Lecturer at Faculty of Law, University of Abuja, FCT, Nigeria. Email: aamubarak@hotmail.com

* Aisha Sani Maikudi, Ph.D, LL.B (1onD), LL.M (LSE), B.L, Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Law, University of Abuja, FCT, Nigeria. E-mail: ayeesha31@yahoo.co.uk; Phone No: 08037040140

Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) in the year 2000, all except two were internal. All of the 15 most deadly conflicts in 2001, those that caused 100 or more deaths, were internal conflicts. Indeed, all but 3 of 57 major armed conflicts registered for 1990–2001 were Non-international. Unfortunately, in SIPRI's 2000 Yearbook, it was stated that, "...Africa is the most conflict ridden region of the World and the only region in which the number of armed conflicts is on the increase"². Again, in its 2002 Yearbook, SIPRI stated that, "Africa continued to be the region with the greatest number of conflicts"³. These domestic conflicts pose a serious threat to economic development, especially for these poor African countries.

In recent years a new type of conflict has come increasingly to the fore: conflict that takes place within and across states, or intra-state conflict, in the form of armed insurrection, violent secessionist movements and other domestic warfare⁴. After the September 11 attacks, United States declared a war on terror on transnational organizations more specifically Al Qaeda⁵. Although, in political terms, the war on terror is correct, there have been controversies as to whether international law recognizes it as an armed conflict. IHL comes into force when a situation is classified as an armed conflict, but the modern dynamics of differentiating terrorism and an armed conflict is vague. Secondly, the status of the individual is complex as it is hard to differentiate a terrorist from a freedom fighter.

Recent armed conflicts in Africa are now intrastate conflicts where people in the same country fight against each other because of different causes. Therefore, although conflicts intend to bring positive results, they have negative effects to youth, children and women because in a conflict, rights of the civilian population are not respected. This article focuses on terrorism as a changing pattern of conflict in Africa and the role that IHL plays to address it within the provisions of its instruments. The authors have the view that IHL, in the provisions of its instruments, does not play a strong role in dealing with terrorism not only in Africa but anywhere in the globe.

- SIPRI (The Stockholm International Peace Research Institute) (2000), Yearbook of World Armaments and Disarmaments. Oxford: Oxford University Press. ¹

- Ibid²

- Ibid³

- like the Boko Haram insurgency in Northern Nigeria, the Tuareg separatists movement in Mali and the violence between armed groups in Libya today. ⁴

- Sassoli, M. (2006), Transnational armed groups and international humanitarian law, Harvard University, 6:1-50 ⁵

2.0 International Humanitarian Law and the Classification of Armed Conflict

There are three types of conflicts that are recognized by international humanitarian law: international armed conflict, internationalized armed conflict, and non-international armed conflict.

International humanitarian law does make it clear what an international armed conflict is. According to the Geneva Conventions of 1949, Common Article 2 states that “all cases of declared war or of any armed conflict that may arise between two or more high contracting parties, even if the state of war is not recognized, the convention shall also apply to all cases of partial or total occupation of the territory of a high contracting party even if the said occupation meets with no armed resistance”⁶. This means that the occurrence of international armed conflict is clear, that is, it would be a conflict between the legal armed forces of two different states. A good example would be the North Korean- South Korean war of 1950.

The second type of conflict recognized by international humanitarian law is a new phenomenon known as 'an internationalized armed conflict'. The situation of an internationalized armed conflict can occur when a war occurs between two different factions fighting internally but supported by two different states⁷. The most visible example of an internationalized armed conflict was the conflict in the Democratic Republic of Congo in 1998 when the forces from Rwanda, Angola, Zimbabwe and Uganda intervened to support various groups in the DRC and also the conflict in the Syrian Arab republic in which Russia and Iran intervened to support Syrian military against insurgents and on the other hand, the US and some European countries are supporting the insurgents against the Syrian troops. Just a week ago⁸ the Turkish army entered Syrian soil in a fresh attack against Kurdish armed group in the region.

The third type of conflict, which are non-international, armed conflicts, according to common article 3 of the Geneva Convention, are ‘armed conflicts that are non-international in nature occurring in one of the High contracting parties’⁹. This means that one of the parties involved is nongovernmental in nature. However, Common Article 3 also states that it does not apply to

⁶ - Geneva Convention, 1949, common art.2

- Stewart, G.S. (2003), Towards a single definition of armed conflict in international humanitarian law: A ⁷ critique of internationalized armed conflict, 85(850):313-350

- 20th of January, 2018.⁸

- Geneva Convention, common article 3, 1949.⁹

other forms of violence such as riots, isolated and sporadic acts of violence. This abstract definition has made it difficult to make a clear distinction between a mere disturbance and an armed conflict, therefore relying heavily on the political will of states to classify the situation as an armed conflict. For a situation to be classified as a non-international armed conflict, it has to achieve two variables: first, the hostilities have to reach a certain minimum level of intensity and form in a collective character¹⁰; and second, there has to be a level of organization of the parties¹¹.

The classification of a situation as an armed conflict means that international humanitarian law comes into force immediately. However, due to certain legal and political reasons various situations are too complex to be considered as armed conflicts.

3.0 Nature of Armed Conflicts in Africa

Civil, internal or non - international wars remain the dominant form of conflict in Africa. However, the number of wars has halved since the 1990s and the nature of the conflicts has changed significantly with the lines between criminal and political violence becoming increasingly blurred. As the World Development Report 2011 states, ‘the remaining forms of conflict and violence do not fit neatly either into “war” or “peace”, or into “criminal violence” or “political violence”¹². The 2011 Global Burden of Armed Violence, therefore, challenges compartmentalized approaches to armed violence. It provides a global overview of different forms of violence, tries to understand how violence manifests in various contexts and how forms of violence interact with one another¹³. Scott Straus provides the following crisp summary on the changing nature of conflict: ‘Today’s wars are typically fought on the peripheries of states, and insurgents tend to be militarily weak and factionalized’¹⁴.

After the collapse of the Berlin Wall in 1989, some previously frozen conflicts in Africa reignited violently, including those in Liberia, Sierra Leone, Rwanda and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). After this pent-up conflict pressure was released, a steady decline ensued. In a number of instances, insurgencies that had been externally funded before and

- Vite, p 75; ICRC, 2008, p 3. ¹⁰

- Ibid ¹¹

- World Bank, World Development Report 2011: Conflict, Security and Development, 2011, 2. - ¹²

- Geneva Declaration Secretariat, Global burden of armed violence 2011, 5f. ¹³

- Scott Straus, ‘Wars do end! Changing patterns of political violence in sub-Saharan Africa, African Affairs’, ¹⁴ 111(443) (2012), 181.

therefore had benefitted financially from the Cold War turned inward for resources. They used diamonds (UNITA and the RUF in Angola), Colton (various factions in the eastern DRC), coffee and cacao (in Côte d'Ivoire), and even charcoal (in Somalia) as alternative sources of revenue. Generally, these 'resource-based insurgencies'¹⁵ were unable to grow into large-scale fighting forces and lacked the strength to challenge the dominant party in the capital. However, there have been exceptions in recent years, such as the extreme cases of Mali, Boko Haram in Nigeria and the Central African Republic (CAR) unrest, where the weakening of the armed forces is significant.

3.1 International (Territorial) Armed Conflicts in Africa.

External conflicts may have economic and political or ideological sources and dimensions. Whatever may be the complexion of their sources, conflicts manifest as territorial or spatial disputes. As a function of differences, which are construed at that time as exclusionary or non-negotiable, the parties to such disputes resort to the use of armed force and other resources against each other, to pursue their respective objectives with regard to the subject matter of the dispute, and such action is inherently territorial. Armed conflicts that involve a comprehensive or systematic mobilization of resources and a persistent resolve and are conducted through stable and resistant command and decision-making structures, even if not caused primarily by territorial claims, have often carried with themselves territorial modifications.

In the contemporary international system, territorial modifications induced through militarized disputes, whether caused by political or ideological differences or by territorial claims, are explicitly prohibited by international law. The turning point in this approach was again World War II, fought by the Allies to deny the Axis powers *inter alia* their plans for a redrawing of the political boundaries across Eurasia and Africa, yet, once the latter were defeated, they were not annexed in whole or part by the former¹⁶. The last, and for that matter the only territorial

- JakkieCilliers, Resource wars – a new type of insurgency, in JakkieCilliers and Christian Dietrich (eds), ¹⁵ Angola's war economy, Peace, profit or plunder? Pretoria: Institute for Security Studies, 2000.

¹⁶- The exceptions concerned standing territorial disputes, such as Silesia, Alsace/Lorraine, and the Kuriles/Northern Hokkaido islands. Exceptions settled through international law agreements may have put an end to those historical disputes. See W. Czapliski, *The New Polish-German Treaties and the Changing Political Structure of Europe*, 86 *American Journal Of International Law* 1 163 (1992); Lovelace, *The Unification of Germany and the Treaty on the Final Settlement*, 49 *International Practitioner's Notebook* (1991). 1990 Treaty on the Final Settlement. Otherwise, the territorial disputes related to those exceptions remain alive. I. e., Kuriles/Northern Hokkaido. The most problematic exception to the general international law prohibition of

modification which has been allowed in Africa as a consequence of an armed conflict, and that has been recognized by the African interstate system and by the international community, was the establishment of a new boundary in northern Ethiopia with the constitution of the Republic of Eritrea as an independent state in 1993¹⁷. That conflict was however not the result of a war between states but an *internal* process of self-determination, undertaken through a *war of national liberation*, which may be legitimate under international law¹⁸.

When does the *pure territorial* conflict arise? The pure territorial conflict is one caused by differences arising from common claims over the same land, river, island and sea areas, or over rights concerning them, such as usage for whatever purposes, usually for economic exploitation, or sometimes for passage and freedom of transit. Technically, under international law, pure territorial conflicts may be of two kinds: those arising from claims derived from state formation processes, and those arising from claims between established states relating to sovereign title over space areas which have remained unsettled or that have been historical objects of dispute between them. There is a fairly wide range of overlap between these two types of pure territorial conflict. One of the most difficult cases takes place when both compound with a third-party's self-determination claims.

Most African conflicts are conflicts historically arising from processes of state formation, where no initial third-party self-determination claims may be necessarily at stake. Conflicts of

territorial modifications through acts of armed force remains the question of the Palestinian territories occupied by Israel after the 1967 war. See Adam Roberts, *Prolonged Military Occupation: The Israeli-Occupied Territories Since 1967*, 84 American Journal of International Law 1 44 (1990).[36A] c1 *Western Sahara*, c2 *Eritrea/Ethiopia*, c3 *Somalia/Somaliland*, c4 *Sudan*, c5 *Guinea-Bissau/Senegal*, c6 *Angola*, c7 *Mozambique*, c8 *Rwanda*, c9 *Burundi*, c10 *Uganda*, c11 *Chad*, c12 *The Congo*, c13 *Burkina Fasso/Mali*, c14 *Botswana/Namibia*, c15 *Libya/Chad*, c16 *Cameroon/Nigeria*, c17 *Tunisia/Libya*, c18 *Sierra Leone*, c19 *Liberia*, c20 *Uganda/Rwanda*, c21 *The Congo/Rwanda/Uganda*, c22 *Nigeria*, c23 *Algeria*. Re. *Law and International Security in Africa* Project, International Studies Program and Center for African Studies, The Ohio State University.

- On Ethiopia's new northern boundary and the constitution of independent Eritrea, see The United Nations ¹⁷ And The Independence Of Eritrea (1996).

¹⁸- On the legitimacy of national liberation wars under international law, see Cassese, *Self-Determination Of Peoples 197-198* (1995); Wilson, *International Law And The Use Of Force By National Liberation Movements* (1988); and the difficult balance act between the principles of selfdetermination and territorial integrity of states, i. e. UNGAR 2625; see Robert Rosenstock, *The Declaration of Principles of International Law Concerning Friendly Relations*, 65 American Journal Of International Law 4 713 (1971); generally, Samuel K. N. Blay, *Self-Determination v. Territorial Integrity in Decolonization*, 18 New York Univ Journal Of Int'l Law & Politics 442 (1986).

that type can be seen between Botswana and Namibia over the Kasikili/Sedudu Island,¹⁹ the land and maritime boundary conflict between Cameroon and Nigeria, mainly centered on the Bakassi peninsula,²⁰ and the dispute between Tunisia and Libya over the northern Gulf of Gabes, which affects their continental shelf²¹. As these conflicts evolve over time, new territorial complexities may emerge. The dispute between Guinea-Bissau and Senegal over their maritime boundaries, initially settled by agreement between Portugal and France in 1960 and rejected by Guinea-Bissau after it achieved independence in 1974, may be considered in principle a conflict arising from their respective processes of state formation, as to what concerns the dimension of having a *defined territory*²². The conflict has then become additionally complicated by the secessionist movement in the Casamance region, in southern Senegal, which has a direct effect on the relations between the two countries and their respective territorial claims, and between them and their neighbors, Gambia, Guinea-Conakry, and now also the Cape Verde Islands, initially in a federation with, but that has now declared its independence from, Guinea-Bissau. The conflict between Libya and Chad presents also certain elements of that pattern, as it compounds with a secessionist movement in northern Chad²³.

The pattern may also be the other way around, where self-determination claims backing secessionist movements' compound with other external processes. There is a growing danger of that situation evolving in the Greater Horn area, as the secessionist movements in southern Sudan and northern Somalia, which has now for all practical purposes become independent Somaliland, compound with the focal Eritrean/Ethiopian war. Comparable conditions may be perceptible in the Great Lakes region, and even in and over the Western Sahara case, affecting again the relations between Algeria and Morocco, and between them and Mauritania.

¹⁹- 1999 ICJ Reports, *Kasikili/Sedudu Island (Botswana v. Namibia)*.

²⁰- 1994- ICJ Reports, *Land and Maritime Boundary between Cameroon and Nigeria (Cameroon v. Nigeria)*.

²¹- 1982 ICJ Reports, *Continental Shelf (Tunisia v Libya)*.

²²- 1995 ICJ Reports, *Maritime Delimitation between Guinea-Bissau and Senegal (Guinea-Bissau v. Senegal)*. See N. Abdulai, *Civil War in Guinea-Bissau*, ACCORD ONLINE (1998), at <<http://www.accord.org.za/publications/ct1/bissau.htm>>.

- 1990-1994 ICJ Reports, *Territorial Dispute (Libya v. Chad)*.²³

3.2 Non-International (Internal) Armed Conflicts in Africa.

Non-international (internal) armed conflict has surfaced as the leading form of violence in Africa²⁴. In the 1990s, all but one of the major conflicts fought in the continent displayed some element of internal strife²⁵. Unfortunately, norms governing internal conflict are underdeveloped (the core protections are Common Article 3 to the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocol II)²⁶. This is unsurprising, for states naturally resist limits on how they may deal with internal matters, particularly given the unlikelihood that their opponents will play by the rules.

Nevertheless, there is a growing sense that what occurs within a state's borders should be the business of others. Operation Allied Force, NATO's 1999 intervention in Yugoslavia, represents the most dramatic illustration. Consider also the global condemnation of the international community's failure to intervene in Rwanda as hundreds of thousands were slaughtered in 1994, as well as international peace operations from the Balkans to East Timor. In the twenty-first century, external interference in other states' internal affairs, even military intervention, increasingly will be deemed legitimate when states turn on their own citizens. Additionally, the international community is finally willing to hold those involved in internal conflicts accountable for their actions. For instance, the ICTY exercises jurisdiction over crimes committed during the internal phases of the Balkan wars, the ICTR addresses abuses that occurred during a purely internal conflict in Rwanda, and International Criminal Court (ICC) jurisdiction extends to an extensive list of offenses during internal conflicts, even when committed by citizens of nonparty states. Also new are hybrid international-national courts like the Special Court for Sierra Leone. Cooperative ventures between the international community and the state that experienced the internal conflict; such tribunals balance legitimate state interests in controlling their own affairs with the community's goal of limiting abuses. Most illustrative of this trend is the Milosevic trial, a prosecution for crimes against humanity and war crimes of a head of state who was turned over by his successors after being defeated in an open election, another is the case of Charles Taylor of Liberia who was also arrested and convicted for war crimes. Also apparent is a growing acceptance of codification in the field. In December 2001, for example, the Conventional Weapons Convention was amended to make

-International Committee of the Red Cross: Weapons that may cause Unnecessary Suffering or have ²⁴ Indiscriminate Effects. Report on the work of a group of experts, Geneva. ICRC, 1973, para.,. 23, p. 13.

-Ibid²⁵

-Ibid²⁶

all four of its operative protocols applicable during non-international armed conflict. Indeed, virtually all of the relevant instruments adopted in the last two decades apply during internal conflict. Similarly, international tribunals are building a body of case law that supports application of *international* armed conflict law to internal hostilities. As the ICTY Appeals Chamber noted in 1995 during the *Tadic*²⁷ case:

“Customary rules have developed to govern internal strife. These rules cover such areas as protection of civilians from hostilities, in particular from indiscriminate attacks, protection of civilian objects, in particular cultural property, protection of all those who do not (or no longer) take active part in hostilities, as well as prohibition of means of warfare prescribed in international armed conflicts and ban of certain methods of conducting hostilities”.²⁸

3.3 New Pattern of Armed Conflicts in Africa.

Today’s conflicts in Africa appear to be increasingly fragmented and the number of actors, particularly non-state factions, involved in conflicts is rising.²⁹ This is evident in regions such as Darfur, in Sudan, where the peace process that was finalized at the All Darfur Stakeholders’ Conference in May 2011 (in Doha, Qatar), was significantly complicated by divisions among various rebel factions. More recently, the Séléka coalition in the CAR (whose advance on the capital, Bangui, was temporarily halted by the intervention of other African countries) eventually consisted of five separate groupings. Three of these signed a peace agreement with President François Bozizé on 13 January 2013. Bozizé was eventually ousted when the coalition resumed their advance a few months later. In the armed conflict in northern Mali, previous allies, Tuareg and Islamist rebels, fought each other in the latter stages of Operation Served in January 2013 when French forces recaptured Mali’s north. Also, in the eastern provinces of the DRC, the M23 rebel movement has recently split into different factions ahead of the decision to deploy a neutral intervention force as part of the United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the DRC. Therefore, scholars recognize ‘the reality of a messy

- Tadić (Jurisdiction) para 126.²⁷

- Ibid²⁸

- The UCDP tabulates the number of actors involved in conflicts and refers to dyads, defined as a pair of ²⁹ warring parties. In interstate conflicts, these warring parties are governments of states, whereas in intrastate conflicts, one is the government of a state and the other is a rebel group. See http://www.pcr.uu.se/digitalAssets/124/124259_conflicts_dyads_2011.pdf (accessed 15 March 2013). For evidence on the increased fragmentation of conflict, see also Themnér and Wallenstein, *Armed conflict, 1946–2011*, 566.

empirical record in which non-state groups are frequently racked by internal differences and struggles³⁰ which complicates the picture of state versus non-state actors.

In addition, several of today's insurgent groups have strong transnational characteristics and move relatively easily across borders and between states. However, few present a significant military threat to governments or are in a position to seize and hold large strips of territory. Some fight on the periphery of fairly well-consolidated states, as in Senegal, Mali and Uganda, whereas others exploit the weak central authority of countries such as the DRC and Sudan.³¹ Another well-known example is al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb, which originally fought to overthrow the Algerian government while consolidating its activities across the Sahel region, particularly in northern Mali. The activity of ISIL militants in Libya, which is going on in some parts of the country, is another pattern of warfare that the African continent is witnessing in recent years. The internal tribal war in South Sudan that left hundreds killed is a new pattern of armed conflict that the African continent is being confronted with.

A number of recent publications by the Institute for Security Studies (ISS) indicate the tendency towards convergence and connection between networks of organized crime as well as their illicit activities, including money laundering, kidnapping, drug trafficking and terrorism³².

4.0 Insurgency, Guerilla Warfare and Terrorist Attacks in Africa.

The most important change in the pattern of armed conflicts that Africa is witnessing in recent years is the change from conventional warfare between armed groups and the state armed forces to insurgency and terrorist attacks by armed groups and counter attacks by the regular armed forces of the sovereign state.

- W. Pearlman and K.G. Cunningham, Non state actors, fragmentation, and conflict processes, *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 56(1), 4; Straus, *Wars do end!*, 181.

-Straus, *Wars do end!*, 181–182; I. Salehan, *Rebels without borders: transnational insurgencies in world politics*, New York: Cornell University Press, 2009.

- Tuesday Reitano and Mark Shaw, *Check your blind spot – confronting criminal spoilers in the Sahel*,³² Institute for Security Studies, Policy Brief, 2013; Lori-Anne Thérout-Bénoni, *Mali in the aftermath of the French military operation*, Institute for Security Studies, Situation Report, 2013; Mark Shaw and Tuesday Reitano, *The evolution of organised crime in Africa: towards a new response*, Institute for Security Studies, Paper 244 (April 2013). All available at www.issafrica.org.

4.1 Terrorism Defined.

There is no universal agreement on the definition of terrorism³³. Various legal systems and government agencies use different definitions³⁴. Moreover, governments have been reluctant to formulate an agreed upon and legally binding definition. These difficulties arise from the fact that the term is politically and emotionally charged³⁵. In the United States of America, for example, Terrorism is defined in Title 22 Chapter 38 U.S. Code § 2656f as "premeditated, politically motivated violence perpetrated against noncombatant targets by subnational groups or clandestine agents"³⁶. According to Matusitz³⁷ terrorism includes the following: it is the use of violence or threat of violence in the pursuit of political, religious, ideological or social objectives; it can be committed by governments, non-state actors, or undercover personnel serving on the behalf of their respective governments; it reaches more than the immediate target victims and is also directed at targets consisting of a larger spectrum of society; and it is both *mala prohibita* (i.e., crime that is made illegal by legislation) and *mala in se* (i.e., crime that is inherently immoral or wrong).

Ben Saul has noted that, "A combination of pragmatic and principled arguments supports the case for defining terrorism in international law"³⁸, including the need to condemn violations to human rights, to protect the state and deliberative politics, to differentiate public and private violence, and to ensure international peace and security. Carlos Diaz-Paniagua, who coordinated the negotiations of the proposed United Nations Comprehensive Convention on International Terrorism, noted, on his part, the need to provide a precise definition of terrorist activities in international law: "Criminal law has three purposes: to declare that a conduct is forbidden, to prevent it, and to express society's condemnation for the wrongful acts. The symbolic, normative role of criminalization is of particular importance in the case of terrorism. The criminalization of terrorist acts expresses society's repugnance at them, invokes social censure and shame, and stigmatizes those who commit them. Moreover, by creating and

- Williamson, Myra (2009). Terrorism, war and international law: the legality of the use of force against Afghanistan in 2001. Ashgate Publishing. p. 38.

- Schmid, Alex P. (2011). "The Definition of Terrorism". The Routledge Handbook of Terrorism Research. Routledge. p. 39.

- Hoffman (1998), p. 23, See the 1 Nov 1998 review by Raymond Bonner in the New York Times of Inside Terrorism

- "law.cornell.edu: "U.S. Code > Title 22 > Chapter 38 > § 2656f - Annual country reports on terrorism"³⁶

- Matusitz, Jonathan (2013). Terrorism & Communication: A Critical Introduction. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage³⁷

- Ben Saul, "Defining 'Terrorism' to Protect Human Rights" in Sydney Law School Legal Studies Research Paper, No. 08-125 (2008) p. 1

reaffirming values, criminalization may serve, in the long run, as a deterrent to terrorism, as those values are internalized"³⁹.

Sami Zeidan, a Lebanese diplomat and scholar, explained the political reasons underlying the current difficulties to define terrorism as follows:

There is no general consensus on the definition of terrorism. The difficulty of defining terrorism lies in the risk it entails of taking positions. The political value of the term currently prevails over its legal one. Left to its political meaning, terrorism easily falls prey to change that suits the interests of particular states at particular times. The Taliban and Osama bin Laden were once called freedom fighters (mujahideen) and backed by the CIA when they were resisting the Soviet occupation of Afghanistan. Now they are on top of the international terrorist lists. Today, the United Nations views Palestinians as freedom fighters, struggling against the unlawful occupation of their land by Israel, and engaged in a long-established legitimate resistance, yet Israel regards them as terrorists. Israel also brands the Hizbullah of Lebanon as a terrorist group, whereas most of the international community regards it as a legitimate resistance group, fighting Israel's occupation of Southern Lebanon. In fact, the successful ousting of Israeli forces from most of the South by the Hizbollah in 2000 made Lebanon the only Arab country to actually defeat the Israeli army. The repercussion of the current preponderance of the political over the legal value of terrorism is costly, leaving the war against terrorism selective, incomplete and ineffective⁴⁰.

To define 'terrorism' in a way that is both all-inclusive and unambiguous is very difficult, if not impossible. One of the principal difficulties lies in the fundamental values at stake in the acceptance or rejection of terror-inspiring violence as means of accomplishing a given goal. The range of views on these issues are what makes an internationally accepted specific definition of what is loosely called 'terrorism,' a largely impossible undertaking. That is why the search for an internationally agreed upon definition may well be a futile and unnecessary effort⁴¹.

- C.F. Diaz-Paniagua, *Negotiating terrorism: The negotiation dynamics of four UN counter-terrorism treaties, 1997-2005*, City University of New York (2008) p. 41

- Sami Zeidan, *Desperately Seeking Definition: The International Community's Quest for Identifying the Specter of Terrorism*, 36 *Cornell International Law Journal*.

- M. Cherif Bassiouni, "A Policy-oriented Inquiry of 'International Terrorism'" in: M. Cherif Bassiouni, ed., *Legal Responses to International Terrorism: U.S. Procedural Aspects*, (Dordrecht, Boston and London: (Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1988)

4.2 Africa and the Rise of Terrorism

The recent deadly terror attack by al Shabaab in Mogadishu, the capital city of Somalia, a suicide bomb attack by Boko Haram in Maiduguri in Nigeria, and an attack on a military post in Mali by an al Qaeda-linked terror group have brought the focus back on terrorism in the African continent. Over the years, terrorism has become the most important challenge to peace, security and development in Africa. The terror activities have grown exponentially in the continent, not only in terms of the number of attacks but also the number of countries affected due to increased proliferation of terrorist groups.

In terms of statistics, according to the IHS Jane's Terrorism and Insurgency Centre, during the period 2009-2015 terror attacks by radical groups in Africa have increased by 200 per cent and fatalities by more than 750 per cent⁴². A number of groups have been terrorising the civilians and governments alike in several parts of Africa. While global terror groups such as the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) and al Qaeda have made their presence felt in the region, other local groups too have gained prominence over the years. The deadliest of these are Boko Haram, Al Qaeda in Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) and Al Shabaab. As a result, an arc of instability is spreading across Africa, from Nigeria in West Africa, Mali in Sahel, Libya in North Africa, to Somalia in East Africa.

In Nigeria, Boko Haram (meaning Western education is a sin) continues to target civilians and government infrastructure despite several rounds of operation conducted by the Nigerian Army. Boko Haram, that came up in 2009, had emerged as the 'world's deadliest terrorist organisation' by 2014. In the last eight years, it is said that Boko Haram has taken 20,000 lives, displaced 2.6 million people, created 75,000 orphans and caused about nine billion dollars worth of damage⁴³. Links with the ISIS and the leadership tussle between Abubakar Shekau and ISIS favouring Abu Musab al-Barnawi, have turned the situation more complex. While there may have been some reduction in Boko Haram-led violence in the country due the Nigerian Army's counter terrorism campaign, the group continues to expand its operations in neighbouring countries such as Cameroon, Niger and Chad⁴⁴.

- "Numbers Show Dramatic Rise of Terrorist Attacks in Africa Over Past Six Years, HIS Says", Business ⁴² Wire, June 27, 2016 (accessed March 30, 2017

- Freedom C. Onuoha, "Split in ISIS-Aligned Boko Haram Group", Al Jazeera Centre for Studies, October ⁴³ (27, 2016 (accessed March 30, 2017

- Ryan Cummings, "Africa's 2017 Terrorism Outlook", Centre on Religion and Geopolitics (accessed March ⁴⁴ (15, 2017

In Sahel, there is a resurgence of al Qaeda. The four terrorist groups that continue to wreak havoc in the region - AQIM, Mokhtar Belmokhtar's al Mourabitoun, Ansar Dine and Macina Liberation Front - have recently decided to combine forces and merge into a single group called Jama'at Nusrat al-Islam wal Muslimeen (Group for Support of Islam and Muslims)⁴⁵. They have also pledged allegiance to the al Qaeda leadership. This regrouping of terror groups is ominous for countries such as Mali and the neighbouring Niger, Cote d' Ivoire and Burkina Faso that have borne the brunt of their attacks in the past.

In Somalia, the notorious al Shabaab is on the offensive and in recent months has taken control of some towns after defeating the troops of the African Union Mission in Somalia (AMISOM)⁴⁶. The group has increased its attacks on African Union bases, Somali government facilities, targets in neighbouring Kenya and, for the first time in a show of strength, has also launched attacks in the northern Puntland autonomous region. This comes as a surprise as the al Shabaab had steadily lost ground over the last six years. It lost control of the capital Mogadishu in 2011 and was then pushed out of Somalia's major cities by the 22,000-strong African Union force deployed in the country. The withdrawal of the Ethiopian troops from Somalia and the announcement by the African Union to withdraw AMISOM too (triggered primarily by reduction in funding by the European Union) may have been to an extent responsible for al Shabaab's comeback. The attacks in the north may be a move to regain control by the pro-al Qaeda al Shabaab leadership, after the recent declaration of allegiance to ISIS by Abdul Qadir Meemen, leader of the faction based in Puntland⁴⁷. Another issue of concern is the possibility of revival of friendship between the al Qaeda of Arabian Peninsula (AQAP) and al Shabaab. In the past, al Shabaab is reported to have trained cadre along with AQAP. The Saudi Arabia-led war against Houthis in Yemen seems to have benefitted the AQAP⁴⁸. This group appears to have rapidly gained control over chunks of territory in Yemen. The emergence of nexus between al Shabaab and AQAP could make the situation in Somalia deadlier.

- "Rising Terror: Extremist groups in Africa's Sahel announce merger", The New Arab, March 03, 2017 ⁴⁵
(accessed March 14, 2017

- Conor Gaffey, "Somalia's Al Shabaab militants ramp up attacks after rejecting President's amnesty offer", ⁴⁶
(Newsweek, April 10, 2017 (accessed April 10, 2017

. - Joshua Meservey, "Al Shabab's Resurgence", The Heritage Foundation, January 04, 2017⁴⁷

- Michael Horton, "Why U.S. troops may fight alongside Al-Qaeda in Yemen", The American Conservative, ⁴⁸
(April 05, 2017 (accessed April 10, 2017

The ISIS plan to establish a caliphate in North Africa was thwarted after it was routed out of Sirte, the last ISIS strong hold, in December 2016 by the Libyan National Army, with air support provided by the United States (US). Since 2014, pro-ISIS terrorist groups have been active in North Africa, particularly in Tunisia and Libya. In Libya, the instability following the collapse of the Muammar al Gaddafi regime, and the presence of numerous indigenous factions and also the porous borders, provided a fertile ground for the expansion of ISIS in the country. Moreover, Libya's long unmonitored coastline too provided the ISIS with a channel to Europe. Between 2014 and 2016, ISIS expanded its presence in multiple cities in Libya, including Derna, Benghazi and Sirte. While the terror group was driven out of most of the region under its control, there are chances that remnants of the group may reconstitute and again create problems. In Tunisia, Ansar al-Sharia, an ISIS affiliate, has been responsible for a large number of terror attacks in the country. It has also been the main facilitator of ISIS fighters from the country to West Asia. Tunisia, has earned the ignominious tag of being the key recruitment ground for the ISIS (about 6,500) in Syria and Iraq⁴⁹. ISIS is recruiting youth from eastern as well as southern Africa to fight its wars in Syria and Libya. In Kenya, coastal Tanzania and Zanzibar, youth from the Muslim communities are vulnerable to the ISIS recruitment drives. Reports suggest that at least 140 youth from South Africa may have joined the ISIS⁵⁰. These terrorist outfits are using both the Internet as well as networks of radical clerics to lure the youth from the region.

4.3 An African Initiative in Combatting Terrorism.

There is a growing recognition in Africa that terrorism is a transnational problem and, therefore, there is a need for cooperation at the continental level to effectively deal with it⁵¹. Over the years, African countries have devised various measures to deal with this threat at the pan-African level. The organization of African Unity (OAU) Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism, adopted at Algiers in 1999, had put in place a solid framework to deal with the scourge of terrorism⁵². It not only defined terrorism but also laid out areas of

- Joseph Siegle, "ISIS in Africa: Implications from Syria and Iraq", Centre for Security Studies, Zurich, ⁴⁹ (March 28, 2017 (accessed March 30, 2017

Rachel Ehrenfeld, "ISIS Growing Presence in Libya Threatens Europe and the U.S", American Center for Democracy, February 19, 2016 (accessed March 27, 2017

- Peter Dube, "Terrorist group Isis makes inroads into southern Africa", Africa Review, September 29, 2015 ⁵⁰ (accessed March 27, 2017

- Simon Allison, "Good talk, not enough action: The AU's counter-terrorism architecture, and why it ⁵¹ (matters)", Institute for Security Studies, Policy Brief 66, March 2015 (accessed March 30, 2017

- "OAU Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism, 1999", African Union Peace and ⁵² Security (accessed March 27, 2017

cooperation among the member states as well as guidelines for the extradition. This was followed by a Plan of Action on Prevention and Combating terrorism in 2002, which put forward several measures for border surveillance, issue of machine readable passports, checking illegal transfer of weapons, introduction of legislation preventing the financing of terrorism, and sharing of information and intelligence on terror activities⁵³. The Plan of Action incorporated international standards for combating terrorism, in line with the provisions of the UNSC Resolution 1373 of September 28, 2001. It also called for the establishment of the African Centre for the Study and Research on Terrorism (ACSRT).

However, the most important instrument is the 2004 Protocol to the 1999 Algiers Convention. This Protocol recognized the “linkages between terrorism and mercenarism, weapons of mass destruction, drug trafficking, corruption, transnational crimes, money laundering and illicit proliferation of small arms”⁵⁴. The Protocol also addressed a major weakness of the 1999 Convention, which is, lack of an implementation mechanism. The 2004 Protocol mandated the African Union’s Peace and Security Council to monitor and facilitate the implementation.

Unfortunately, despite the existence of these instruments, terror networks continue to operate in the region. This is mainly due to the tardy implementation of the counter terrorism framework by the member states. For example, the 2004 Counter Terrorism Protocol needed ratification by minimum 15 states before it could come into force. However, it took more than a decade to finally operationalise this key instrument in 2014. Moreover, some of the key states facing terror attacks such as Nigeria, Kenya, Somalia and Chad are yet to ratify it. Much of the delay has to do with insufficient financial resources and lack of necessary political will amongst African states to implement it.

5.1 Terrorism and Counterterrorism, is International Humanitarian Law Applicable?

The rise of non-State armed groups resorting to acts of terrorism, and the subsequent rallying of a number of other non-State armed groups around them are being witnessed in recent years. States and the United Nations have reacted to these developments by tightening existing counterterrorism measures and/or legislation and by introducing new ones. There is no doubt that it is legitimate to take responsive action to ensure State security. However, in doing so, it

-“Plan of Action of the African Union High-level Inter-Governmental Meeting on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism in Africa”, Algiers, Algeria, September 11-14, 2011, African Centre for the Study and Research on Terrorism (accessed March 27, 2017)

- “Protocol to the OAU Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism”, Addis Ababa, July 08, 2004, African Union Peace and Security (accessed March 30, 2017)

is indispensable to maintain the safeguards protecting human life and dignity laid down in IHL⁵⁵.

Counterterrorism responses, combined with a robust counterterrorism discourse in both domestic and international fora, have significantly contributed to a blurring of the lines between armed conflict and terrorism, with potentially adverse effects on IHL. There appears to be a growing tendency among States to consider any act of violence carried out by a non-State armed group in armed conflict as being "terrorist" by definition, even when such acts are in fact lawful under IHL. This is in parallel to the longstanding concern of some States that recognizing the existence of an armed conflict in their territory would "legitimize" the non-State armed groups involved. The overall result is a denial that such groups, designated as "terrorist," may be a party to a NIAC within the meaning of IHL. The above-mentioned developments have put the issue of the relationship between the legal frameworks governing IHL and terrorism back into the spotlight⁵⁶.

5.2 Distinguishing Between the Legal Frameworks Governing IHL and Terrorism.

The ICRC outlined its position on this issue in its report on IHL and the challenges of contemporary armed conflicts submitted to the 31st International Conference⁵⁷. Given the current trends in counterterrorism, some aspects are worth recalling. In the ICRC's view, the normative regimes governing armed conflict and terrorism should not be confused. While the legal frameworks governing terrorism and IHL may have some common grounds – IHL expressly prohibits most acts that are criminalized as "terrorist" in domestic legislation and

- See the report "International humanitarian law and the challenges of contemporary armed conflicts", section 55 II.2 : The geographic reach of IHL applicability

- In this context, it should be recalled that the criteria that must be fulfilled for a person to be deemed a ⁵⁶ mercenary under Additional Protocol I (Article 47) have rarely been proven to be met in practice. It should also be recalled that the scope of application, the definition and the obligations enunciated in the International Convention against the Recruitment, Use, Financing and Training of Mercenaries (adopted 4 December 1989, entered into force 20 October 2001), 2163 UNTS 75, and the Convention on the Elimination of Mercenarism in Africa (adopted 3 July 1977, entered into force 22 April 1985), OAU Doc. CM/433/Rev. L. Annex 1 (1972), are wider for States parties thereto.

- Extract from the report "International humanitarian law and the challenges of contemporary armed conflicts", document prepared by the ICRC for the 32nd International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent (Geneva, Switzerland, 8-10 December 2015)

international conventions dealing with terrorism – these two legal regimes remain fundamentally different. They have distinct rationales, objectives and structures.

A crucial difference is that, in legal terms, armed conflict is a situation in which certain acts of violence are considered lawful and others are unlawful, while any act of violence, which is designated as "terrorist" is always unlawful. The ultimate aim of an armed conflict is to prevail over the enemy's armed forces. For this reason, the parties to a conflict are permitted, or at least are not prohibited from, attacking each other's military objectives or individuals not entitled to protection against direct attacks. Violence directed at those targets is not prohibited as a matter of IHL, regardless of whether it is inflicted by a State or a non-State party. Acts of violence directed against civilians and civilian objects are, by contrast, unlawful, as one of the main purposes of IHL is to spare them from the effects of hostilities. IHL thus regulates both lawful and unlawful acts of violence. There is no such dichotomy in the norms governing acts of terrorism. The defining feature of any act that is legally classified as "terrorist," whether under domestic or international law is that it is always penalized as criminal. Thus, no act of violence legally designated as "terrorist" is, or can be, exempt from prosecution.

Another main difference between these legal frameworks is the principle of equality of belligerents, pursuant to which the parties to an armed conflict have the same rights and obligations under IHL (even if this is not the case under domestic law). This principle reflects the fact that IHL does not aim to determine the legitimacy of the cause pursued by the belligerents. Its goal, instead, is to ensure the equal protection of persons and objects affected by an armed conflict, irrespective of the lawfulness of the first resort to force. The legal framework governing acts of terrorism obviously does not contain a similar principle. In this context it is important to recall that, while IHL does foresee equal rights and obligations of belligerents in the conduct of hostilities and in the treatment of persons in their power, it does not confer legitimacy on non-State armed groups that are a party to a NIAC. Common Article 3 explicitly states that when parties to a conflict apply its provisions, this "shall not affect the legal status of the Parties to the conflict." Additional Article 3 of Protocol II contains a similar provision guaranteeing the sovereignty of States and their responsibility to maintain law and order, national unity and territorial integrity by all legitimate means⁵⁸.

- Extract from the report "International humanitarian law and the challenges of contemporary armed conflicts", document prepared by the ICRC for the 31st International Conference of the Red Cross and Red Crescent (Geneva, Switzerland, December 2014).

The above does not mean that some overlap cannot be created between the legal regimes governing IHL and terrorism. IHL prohibits both specific acts of terrorism committed in armed conflict and, as war crimes, a range of other acts of violence when committed against civilians or civilian objects. If States choose to additionally designate such acts as "terrorist" under international or domestic law, this will in effect duplicate their criminalization.

However, acts that are not prohibited by IHL – such as attacks against military objectives or against individuals not entitled to protection against direct attacks – should not be labeled "terrorist" at the international or domestic levels (although they remain subject to ordinary domestic criminalization where a NIAC is involved). Attacks against lawful targets constitute the very essence of an armed conflict and should not be legally defined as "terrorist" under another regime of law. To do so would imply that such acts must be subject to criminalization under that legal framework, therefore creating conflicting obligations of States at the international level. This would be contrary to the reality of armed conflicts and the rationale of IHL, which does not prohibit attacks against lawful targets.

Adding another layer of incrimination by designating acts that are not unlawful under IHL as "terrorist" may also discourage IHL compliance by non-State armed groups party to a NIAC. Any motivation they may have to fight in accordance with IHL would likely erode if, irrespective of the efforts they may undertake to comply with it, all of their actions are deemed unlawful. Furthermore, labeling acts that are lawful under IHL as "terrorist" is likely to render the implementation of Article 6(5) of Additional Protocol II – whose objective is to grant the broadest possible amnesty to persons having participated in the hostilities without having committed serious violations of IHL – more difficult. For obvious reasons, the prospect of an amnesty is diminished where even lawful acts of war have been qualified as acts of terrorism. This can ultimately prove to be an obstacle to peace negotiations and reconciliation efforts.

International humanitarian law's main challenge has been the legal status of an individual as to whether he is a terrorist or a combatant especially in non-international armed conflicts⁵⁹ and

- ICRC (2007), *International Humanitarian Law and the challenges of contemporary armed conflicts*, ⁵⁹ Geneva, (30IC/07/8.4)

in situations of self-determination⁶⁰. According to the ICRC, states engaged in non-international armed conflicts have, with increasing frequency, labeled any act committed by domestic insurgents an act of “terrorism” even though, under IHL, such an act might not have been unlawful (e.g. attacks against military personnel or installations). The classification of a situation to be an armed conflict means that international humanitarian law comes into force immediately; this means that it provides a framework for the behavior of belligerent parties and the protection of non-combatants and the respect of the environment and the property of civilians.

The failure to classify a state of affairs as an armed conflict has grave legal and humanitarian consequences. This is because, International humanitarian law has a close relationship with human rights law that aims to protect the rights and dignity of civilians during peace and armed conflict with parties of the conflict having legally binding obligations concerning the rights of persons not involved in the conflict⁶¹.

6.0 Conclusion.

In conclusion, terrorism and counterterrorism are modern dynamics that emerged as armed conflict in Africa within a decade. As a result, in addition to the legal classification of armed conflict under international humanitarian law, another way of resorting to violence as a means of achieving certain political aims has emerged in Africa, which can be deemed as changing the pattern of conflict in the African continent. The politics behind classification of armed conflicts has often brought about the failure of international humanitarian law in playing its part. For international humanitarian law to play a crucial part, it needs to adapt and continuously evolve to cater for the changing dynamics of conflicts experienced today in Africa and elsewhere.

- Chadwick (1996) *Self-determination, terrorism and international humanitarian law*, 1st ed. Hague: Martinus⁶⁰ Nijhoff Publishers

- United Nations (2010), *Report of the Office of the High Commissioner on the outcome of the expert⁶¹ consultation on the issue of protecting the human rights of civilians in armed conflict*, New York: United Nations (A/HRC/14/40)

United States District court for the District of Columbia Civil Action No. 04-1519 (JR)